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 Textiles, Dyeing & Processing, Color Engg, Applied Law & Criminology
 Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
 Indian Government Award Winner (IRS Awards-2025)
 Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
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International Research Consultant

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 Course Curriculum of Research, Applied Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High
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 Analysis & Reporting, Quality in Higher Education, Research Journal, Entrepreneur),
 Specialized Professor of Courses & Research in BSc Engg, MTech, MPhil, Postdoc & PhD in
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Total Years of Academic & Professional Experience (2006-2025): 19 years

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Key note of handwritten book

MTech Thesis on Textile Engineering, MTech Book on Advance Textile Technology, Publication in Textile Engineering, and Conference Presentation on Textile Engineering have been attached for contribution on Textile Engineering under affiliation of University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India

Hossain, M. A. (2015a, 26th April, 2015). *Integrated dyeing and cosmetic finishing on cotton fabric* 6th all India Inter Engineering college academic meet-2015 and Science & Technology exhibition for a sustainable society, Organised by Forum of Scientist, Engineers & Technologists (FOSET), 15N, Nelli Sengupta Sarani (Lindsay Street), Kolkata-700087, India. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29340.26244>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13304637>

Hossain, M. A. (2015b). *Textile coloration and fragrance finishing for perfumed garments* [Textile Technology, University of Calcutta, 35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata-70019, West Bengal, India.]. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15918.48965>; <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7854437>

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Samanta, A. K., Hossain, A., Bagchi, A., & Bhattacharya, K. (2016). Simultaneous Dyeing and Fragrance Finishing of Cotton Fabric. *Journal of Materials Sciences and Applications*, 2(4), 25-34. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16757.35048>

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 Textile/Defence/Law/Education/Home Ministry, Parliament/Government of Any Country,
 Crime Analysis & Reporting, Quality in Higher Education, Research Journal, Entrepreneur),
 Specialized Professor of Courses & Research in BSc Engg, MTech, MPhil, Postdoc & PhD in
 Textile Engg, Postdoc & PhD in Law, Legal Practitioner/Barrister
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Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry,
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 University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
 Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2,
 Dhaka, Bangladesh
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 Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange
 Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite
 Ltd, Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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 Australia
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 Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court,
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 Textile/Defence/Law/Education/Home Ministry, Parliament/Government of Any Country,
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 Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange
 Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite
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Hossain, M. A. (2023bl). *PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21433.34402>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12747607>

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 Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court,
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Self-declared certificate on Professor (Textile Engineering), (2023cb).
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Hossain, M. A. (2023f). *Services for crime in higher education & quality enhancement in an international platform*. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; (engr.anowar@yahoo.com).
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26551.70569>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8278997>

Hossain, M. A. (2023g). *Services for crime protection and crime analysis for the peace of mankind in an international platform*. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36618.03522>;
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Hossain, M. A. (2023cf). *Specialized services and payment rate of Professor (Dr.) Md. Anowar Hossain*. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia.
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- Hossain, M. A. (2023ci). Video reporting for removal of executive suspension and reporting to withdraw of executive suspension when Australian schooling compliance was breached for my PhD candidature in PhD school through the official act of hidden life threatening of PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain (Part-01). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33752.88325>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8154453>; <https://youtu.be/86cxLN3Z9ro>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023cj). Video reporting for removal of executive suspension and reporting to withdraw of executive suspension when Australian schooling compliance was breached for my PhD candidature in PhD school through the official act of hidden life threatening of PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain (Part-02). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.24105.98403>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8162633>; <https://youtu.be/OWXVkgicfKg>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024a). Advancement in UV-Vis-IR camouflage Textiles for concealment of defense surveillance against multidimensional combat background. *Journal of Materials Science: Materials in Engineering*. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40712-024-00182-8>; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.17601.12648>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14282484>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024b). Australian Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist asked 100000 Australian penalty unit to Hon Mark Dreyfus KC MP, Australian Attorney General/law minister of Australian Government. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14776.72967>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10556279>
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- Hossain, M. A. (2024d). Cyber securities for protection of cyber-crimes. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14367.98729>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10841349>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024e). A follow-up letter to The Hon Jason Clare MP, Education Minister, Australia for the conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment in Australian PhD school. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18413.19685>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10964382>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024f). Journal Peer Review Report of PhD Thesis of “Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist” on “Camouflage Textiles with Technical Coloration Incorporating Illumination under Multidimensional Combat Backgrounds” School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36270.32328>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13182515>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024g). Letter to Nobel committee for Nobel prize in camouflage physics. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36807.51367>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10842435>
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- Hossain, M. A. (2024i). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is searching research fund for surviving in research profession and self-learning. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22732.42888>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13997939>

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 Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
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 Commission, PhD/Postdoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Research, Applied Law,
 Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court,
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 Textile/Defence/Law/Education/Home Ministry, Parliament/Government of Any Country,
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 Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2,
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 Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design
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 Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange
 Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite
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 Australia
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- Hossain, M. A. (2024j). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is asking to Ms. Nardia Simpson, Australian High Commissioner for approving the extension of Australian Student VISA for legal and ethical claiming to Australian court under the ethical support of Minister of home affairs, foreign affairs and education. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14584.05126>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14699107>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024k). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President; and Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Chief Advisor of Bangladesh to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22210.80326>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14837268>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024l). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking support of 'free of cost google drive (2TB) access' to Pichai Sundararajan, Chief Executive Officer, Google against the e-mail address of engranowar06@gmail.com. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28761.94568>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13994976>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024m). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is self-nominating for 'global excellence award' at Functional Textiles and Clothing (FTC), Indian Institute of Technology (IIT), Delhi, India under the category of 'Leadership in Research' and/or 'Emerging Innovator' under the invitation of FTC team, IIT, Delhi, India. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36325.61929>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14213757>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024n). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist is asking an exemption of visa fees for the 'Australian global talent permanent residence visa (subclass 858)' under the Australian migration act 45C (c), 1958 and 500.211,1994. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25869.14560>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12754106>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024o). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist is the first inventor of '2100–4200-point policy for the impact factor to certify researcher for PhD degree by Research' and 'PhD in PhD'. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35642.20167>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12604715>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024p). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist is the first inventor of a 1150–2300-point policy to certify or review a research manuscript or thesis for publication R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; engr.anowar@yahoo.com. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.30482.88003>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12735576>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024q). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is asking 'honorary doctorate degree' to the Vice Chancellor of University of Calcutta for his contribution of PhD harassment at RMIT University. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.20869.15843>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10842021>

- Hossain, M. A. (2024r). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is asking 'honorary doctorate degree' to the Vice Chancellor of University of Dhaka for his contribution of PhD harassment at RMIT University*. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36388.08325>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10841964>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024s). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is searching a good-looking lady for his marriage, a requirement of RMIT PhD school*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13112.97282>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12747830>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024t). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 1100–2200-point policy for the impact factor to admit/appoint researcher position for Master degree by research*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.12531.75048>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11516770>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024u). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 1250–2500-point policy for the impact factor to certify university designation and university promotion from lecturer to professor*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13177.68968>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11183360>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024v). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 7050–14100-point policy for the impact factor or ranking of an international standard University*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25604.13447>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10814275>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024w). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the inventor of 10-point policy to elect the democratic leaders all over the world*. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19343.76968>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10662617>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024x). *Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist represented his photographic memories of profession in textile engineering and casual life journey*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32669.69609>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10449995>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024y). *Research services, journal peer reviews, and editorial support of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15157.90080>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13142538>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024). *Seeking VISA extension, legal support, legal costs, legal insurance support, accommodation costs, fooding costs, personal safety, PhD compensation award of Australian Government, PhD compensation award of RMIT University, PhD certificate, PhD mark sheets or academic transcript and job offer letter to Australian Home affairs*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.34569.04960>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13822693>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024z). *A self-understanding of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist about Bangladeshi Nobel laureate Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus and law implementation of Bangladesh Government*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26912.35846>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10461097>
- Hossain, M. A. (2025). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is requesting to Mr. António Guterres, Secretary-General of United Nations for a legal stipend or legal award to proceed with legal proceeding of life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35976.12805>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14934539>
- Hossain, M. A., & Samanta, A. (2018). *Green Dyeing On Cotton Fabric Demodulated From Diospyros Malabarica and Camellia Sinensis with Green Mordanting Agent*. *Latest Trends in Textile and Fashion Designing*, 2(2), 1-8. <http://dx.doi.org/10.32474/LTTFD.2018.02.000132>

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 Textiles, Dyeing & Processing, Color Engg, Applied Law & Criminology
 Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
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 Commission, PhD/Postdoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Research, Applied Law,
 Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court,
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 Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2,
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 Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design
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 Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange
 Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite
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